

X-RAY DIFFRACTION STUDIES OF GUAR GUM, POLYACRYLONITRILE AND THEIR COMPOSITES

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Abstract

Objective- A suitable analytical method is applied for studying the crystallinity, crystallite size and inter-planer distance in order to investigate compatibility of polymers.

Approach- X-ray diffraction and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) were carried out for thin films of guar gum (GG) - a natural polymer, polyacrylonitrile (PAN) - a synthetic polymer, GG grafted with PAN (GG-g-PAN), and a layered composite of GG and PAN (GG/PAN).

Findings- It explains the relation between crystallinity and mechanical strength of composite polymers. SEM result approves better compatibility in GG-g-PAN in comparison with GG/PAN. The composite, GG-g-PAN has been observed to have better crystallinity, mechanical strength and morphology than GG/PAN.

Limitations- X-ray diffraction patterns is an approximate method to calculate about crystallinity of thin films.

Practical implication- The present work will give insight into application of these films.

Originality- The present work is carried out by author to characterized thin films of polymers & their composites prepared in her earlier publications.

Keywords: Guar gum, polyacrylonitrile, polymer composite, XRD, SEM.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite polymers find wide industrial applications because of their improved properties [6, 8, and 9]. Hybridization of the natural polymers with synthetic polymers is of great interest because of its application to biomedical and biodegradable materials [5, 7]. Crystallinity of composite polymers could be enhanced by the various types of processing of homopolymers. Grafting involves attachment of polymer chains, usually monomer, to the back-bone polymer. This has been used to enhance the compatibility between the homopolymers. X-ray diffraction is one of the most powerful techniques for analysis of regular arrangement of lattice units. Even if the regular arrangement is very imperfect, X-rays produce maxima. A number of workers have used X-ray diffraction technique for structural analysis of polymers and composites [3, 5, 7, 12, 15]. Many plastics are partly crystalline, composed of very long molecules, generally in a state of great disarray but organized into ordered regions called crystallites. These regions produce broad diffraction lines. By comparing the intensity and width of line, degree of crystallinity and crystallite size can be estimated [4].

Guar gum (GG) [1] is an edible carbohydrate polymer which is useful as a thickening agent for water and as a reagent for absorption and hydrogen bonding with mineral and cellulosic surface. It is a cold-water swelling polymer. Water is the only common solvent for GG, although it tolerates limited concentrations of water miscible

Pratima & Ramrakhiani / X-Ray Diffraction Studies of Guar Gum, Polyacrylonitrile and Their Composites

solvents such as alcohol. Commercial GG solutions are typically turbid. The turbidity is largely caused by the presence of insoluble portions of the endosperm. It swells in cold water to form highly viscous solutions at very low concentrations. It is, therefore used as a viscosity builder and water binder in explosives, foods, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, mining and paper and textile industries.

Polyacrylonitrile (PAN) is a synthetic acrylic polymer, which finds applications in a variety of industries such as textiles, etc. It is used as a substitute for wood. PAN and pyrolysed PAN have found applications in solar energy conversion systems.

The above two polymers are immiscible to each other. It has been attempted to produce mixed polymer by combining GG and PAN in two different ways; one by depositing alternate layers of GG and PAN and the other by graft polymerization. Present paper reports the X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopic (SEM) studies of GG, PAN and their composites.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Guar gum (GG)

Commercial GG was purified by dissolving in water and reprecipitating in methanol (AR, BDH). The structure of GG is as follows:

2.2 Polyacrylonitrile (PAN)

PAN was prepared by polymerizing acrylonitrile, using redox initiator acrylonitrile (Fluka), which was distilled under vacuum after removing the stabilizer. Acrylonitrile was polymerized in an aqueous medium, using persulphate-ascorbic acid redox initiator at $35^{\circ} \pm 0.2^{\circ}$ C. PAN, which was precipitated in a reaction flask, filtered, washed several times and then dried. The molecular weight of PAN was found to be 952,400 as determined by the viscosity method. The structure of polyacrylonitrile is as follows:

2.3 Film formation

Thin films of polymers were prepared by the solution casting method. A solution containing a particular polymer was poured onto an optically plane glass plate which was kept over a mercury pool. The solvent was then allowed to evaporate slowly at room temperature for 24h. The films were removed and kept in an oven at slightly higher temperature to remove all traces of solvent.

2.4 Guar gum/ Polyacrylonitrile composite (GG/PAN)

Initially, a thin layer of PAN was deposited, using dimethylformamide (DMF) as solvent. On this, a layer of GG was formed. After drying, again a layer of PAN was deposited in same way. In this manner a number of alternate layers of PAN and GG were deposited and this was taken as PAN-GG composite (GG/PAN).

2.5 Guar gum-grafted-polyacrylonitrile (GG-g-PAN)

Graft copolymerization was carried out using a chemical initiating system, viz. persulphate-ascorbic acid. Calculated amounts of GG, acrylonitrile and ascorbic acid were taken in 25 ml of water in a 250 ml reaction flask and thermostated at $35^{\circ} \pm 0.2^{\circ}$ C. After 30 minutes, a known quantity of persulphate was added and the time of addition of persulphate was taken as zero time. After 1 h the reaction was stopped and the graft copolymer was separated by pouring the ingredients into a flask containing a large quantity of dimethylformamide (DMF) wherein the (PAN) was dissolved. GG-grafted-PAN was filtered and weighed in order to determine the percentage grafting and polymer load. The reaction and structure of grafted polymer are as follows:

Its film was also formed in similar manner as described earlier.

2.6 Measurement

All the four samples were subjected to following investigations:

(a) The X-ray diffraction studies were carried out using Model Dmax IIIC RIGAKU

(Japan) at the Thapar Corporate Research and Development Centre, Patiala. The

intensity versus 2θ profile was obtained using automatic step scanning and strip-chart recorder.

(b) In order to investigate the surface morphology of composite polymers, the SEM micro-graphs of all the four samples were recorded by scanning electron microscope. SEM study was conducted by using JEOL, Model JSM 840A (Japan) at the Thapar Corporate Research and Development Centre, Patiala.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The X-ray diffraction profiles of all the four samples are shown in Fig. 1. Comparing the diffraction patterns the following points can be noticed;

(i) In case of pure GG, there is a broad peak. Mean curve drawn shows peak at $2\theta = 18^{\circ}$

Pratima & Ramrakhiani / X-Ray Diffraction Studies of Guar Gum, Polyacrylonitrile and Their Composites

- (ii) In case of pure PAN, there is one sharp peak at $2\theta = 17.2^\circ$ and one low and broad peak at 26.12° .
- (iii) By the combining PAN with GG layer by layer, i.e., in GG/PAN (COM), again mean curve show peak at $2\theta = 18^\circ$.
- (iv) By grafting of PAN with GG, i.e. in GG-g-PAN (GFT), there are two narrow peaks at $2\theta = 17.88^\circ$ and 23.3° . Among them one is intense peak. This shows crystallinity and good regularity in particular directions.

Figure 1: The X-ray diffraction profiles of GG, PAN and their Composites

From the diffraction patterns of various polymer samples inter-planer distance, crystallite size and crystallinity have been computed for different peaks. These are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Parameters from X-ray diffraction

S. No.	Polymer sample	Peaks at 2θ (in degrees)	Intensity (in cps)	Inter-planer distance (in Å.)	Crytallite size (in Å.)	Crystallinity (in %)
1.	GG	18	345	4.92	5.05	not Crystalline
2.	PAN	17.2	266	5.15	58.61	76.6%
3.	GG/PAN	18	500	4.92	6.33	not Crystalline
4.	GG-g-PAN	17.8 23.3	497 274	4.97 3.83	198 136	92.5% 90.1%

The inter-planner distance (d) has been calculated for the peaks obtained in the diffraction patterns using the Bragg's formula:

$$d = \frac{\lambda}{2 \sin \theta} \quad \dots (1)$$

Where, λ is the wavelength of X-rays and θ is the Bragg's angle.

The diffracted beams become diffused when crystal size is nearly the same as the wavelength of the incident beam. Therefore the divergence of X-ray beam is able to give the crystallite size. The relation ship between crystallite size, (Cs) and diffracted ray line broadening is given by Scherrer formula [2] as:

$$C_s = \frac{k\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} \quad \dots (2)$$

Where, β is pure diffraction broadening and k is a constant depending upon the crystalline shape, usually taken as unity. The crystallite size or the distance upto which regular arrangement of layers exists in a particular direction have been calculated from the diffraction broadening of the lines and given in Table 1.

Crystallinity is a measure of regularity in the arrangement of structural elements. Here the crystallinity has been measured on the premise that increasing amorphousness tends to broaden the line width, whereas increasing the crystallinity increases the intensity. The height ($C_r H$) of the peak above its adjacent minimum represents the crystallinity of the sample and the width ($A_m W$) of the peak at this adjacent minimum is considered to represent the amorphousness of the sample [14].

The Crystallinity C_r is calculated from the relation:

$$C_r = 1 - t(A_m W / C_r H) \quad \dots (3)$$

Pratima & Ramrakhiani / X-Ray Diffraction Studies of Guar Gum, Polyacrylonitrile and Their Composites

Where, t is the scale factor relating the height of C_iH to full scale (total blackness). The Crystallinity of the polymer samples has been computed from the diffraction pattern and the values are given in the Table 1.

It is clear that high crystallinity (76.6%) is present in case of PAN having inter-planar distance of 5.15 Å. The regular arrangement of planes is up to 58.61 Å i. e., more than 10 layers. Use of such polymer can be suggested to increase the crystallinity in GG. It is obvious from Table I that in COM, inter-planer distance is 4.92 Å i. e., same as in GG, but crystallite size is little greater -6.33 Å as compared to 5.05 Å in pure GG. Both GG and GG/PAN layered composite are not found to be crystalline. In case of GG-g-PAN, the crystallinity as well as crystallite size are found to be much greater than other samples. Two sharp peaks are observed in XRD pattern giving crystallite size of 198 and 136 Å i. e. about 40 to 50 regular layers and crystallinity of the order of 90%. The mechanical strength of GG-g-PAN was found to be more as compared to its constituents and composite GG/PAN [10]. Thus, increased crystallinity in GG-g-PAN can be attributed to its greater strength. However, in case of GG/ PAN, it seems that diffusion of PAN in GG takes place only at a few places. Hence, its crystalline features are in between that of PAN and GG.

Fig. 2 shows typical scanning electron micrographs of GG, PAN, GG/PAN and GG-g-PAN samples. The morphological survey indicates that PAN has a regular surface, when mixed with GG uneven component appears on the surface in GG/PAN. This may be due to non homogeneous dispersion of GG in PAN. But in case of GG-g-PAN, GG has been uniformly dispersed in polymeric matrix. This result is in coexistence with XRD studies where GG-g-PAN shows high crystallinity than GG/PAN.

3. SCOPE FOR FUTURE WORK

The thin films of GG, PAN and their composite can be subjected to Fourier transform interferometry and differential calorimetry for further characterization.

4. CONCLUSION

Layered and grafted composite polymers of GG and PAN can be formed which are otherwise immiscible. Addition of PAN into GG increase the crystalline phase more in case of grafted sample than layered sample. Increased molecular weight (about 220,000) and network structure of GG-g-PAN results in greater strength as compared to GG/PAN specimen [14]. This suggests correlation between crystallinity and mechanical strength of polymerblends [15][11].

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Figure 2: The SEM photographs of GG, PAN and their Composites

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Pratima & Ramrakhiani / X-Ray Diffraction Studies of Guar Gum, Polyacrylonitrile and Their Composites

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